

Towards a New Poetics: The Splintered Genre in Form in English Language Literature.

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***Abstract:** This discussion attempts to examine why some attempts of creative writing are categorized as Literature while other attempts are relegated to being mere fiction. The discussion posits that the act engaging in this form of art results in the construction and consumption of artifice. Furthermore, discussion of the artifice has produced false conclusions in scholarship. The discussion is intended to be a part of the forthcoming work "Towards a New Poetic", and the discussion is by no means complete. This selection merely contains the ideas that have been developed.*

What is surprising about how English Language Literature¹ is conceptualized is that it is something that only really came into being after the World War I. Despite that fact that English Language Literature has been lumped together with the concept of all Literature, and despite the fact that it has by and large been foisted upon students as this thing that dates back to Beowulf, the antecedents of English Language Literature date back to the only first Degree program beginning in 1829², and then only after World War One did the current conceptualization actually develop as a reaction to the teaching methodology employed until this event. Both writers and scholars after the cataclysmic event of the First World War embarked on separating textual content into either Fiction or Literature and through this the separation seeped into the classifications based upon the aesthetic merit of Entertainment verse Education. Penny Fiction became the Dime Novel, and with that the rise, or fall, of historical value. English Language Literature came to be this thing that is beyond the property of the masses. It became the possession of the initiated elite as a means of Intellectual Gentrification.

Consider what is known about the performance of Shake-

spere's plays. Originally performed in The Globe Theater at the end of the 16th century, they were performed as entertainment, and not because they were scholarly works. If Eliot's assumptions about "Hamlet and his Problems" is ignored, and the true information in the play itself is examined from a scholarly endeavor the play itself is a historical impossibility. Remember, the concept of the suspension of disbelief had not been introduced yet. The audience did not care what Norway was about. Hamlet's inability to be attached to that pressure did not enter into the question of Hamlet's sanity. The threat is pointed out in the play, but it is not a feature of the play because it provides no value to the entertainment. In the history of humanity, mankind has always been more concerned with the sufferings of his fellow man. Aristotle's treatment in Poetics is dependent upon such suffering.

The problem of approaching any type of discussion that is scholarly of English Language Literature defaults to a discussion of words and their meanings. This is of great value if the endeavor is to understand communication but expanding it past that boundary into the realm of a phenomenological concern becomes inexplicably confused. Discovering the value beyond personal preference as a means for justifying the importance of the inquiry and thereby elevating the revelations which follow creates a barrier between the text and humanity. The collision of text and humanity which occurred after The Great War was brought about by the removal of the Ontological connections inherent across the world. Hermeneutic and Phenomenological concerns had developed to a point where by there could be some semblance of the text to humanity, but the calamity that destroyed faith also destroyed that link.

Be that as it may, before pursuing this discussion any further, consideration must be given to this thing which is often taught as the "Rise of the Novel." The Written Form underwent three major transitions: From the poetic form, then to the dramatic form, and then to the narrative form. These transitions were both irregular because the subsequent forms did not replace, and because each

form continued to develop on their own. The most interesting thing about these transitions is that the content is repetitive while the context becomes more fluid. The culmination reached by the 20th century resulted in a re-defining of English Language Literature into the group of artifice {Literature | Fiction | Poetry | Drama}, with the first two components occupying a majority of the scholarship and discussion. Yet, finding the distinction to elevate the two most prominent artifice in this group into a hierarchy of prominent versus popular as a means for establishing a need by, for, and of humanity was difficult. Even today, understanding that F. Scott Fitzgerald's *The Great Gatsby* is merely a retelling of Joseph Conrad's *The Heart of Darkness* offers enormous difficulties in and of itself. This is compounded by the widely accepted perception that *The Great Gatsby* is "the Great American novel". The overall topoi of both texts are the exploitation of reputation leading to destruction. The minor elements of each work may differ making recognition that the latter's formulaic construction is merely a repetition of the former's. Yet, while Conrad's work may never have enjoyed the popularity of Fitzgerald's, it has always maintained a prominence beyond it. The truly remarkable feature of this association is there has been little scholarship that maps the formula of each work in comparison. Given Fitzgerald's admiration and obsession with Conrad, few would consider Fitzgerald's work just another dime novel. Yet, what this duplication reveals is that it is not the exception to the rule, but the rule: The chief concern of the novel has always been the tragic human condition leading to either death or marriage. (What can be considered the "Disney Ending".)

Perhaps one of the most difficult aspects of this discussion is that all Literature is a form of Fiction, but not all Fiction can be considered Literature. Furthermore, Fiction before form is all inclusive. Fiction is a definition that does include Poetry and Drama through narrative form. Differentiating Drama is easily achieved through recognition of its application as an artifice: it is not intended to be read but performed. Even though Poetry and to a lesser

extend Fiction can be performed—and among Poets this may be cause to object—both of these types are artifices wherein reading achieves completion. Be that as it may, the aesthetic purpose remains external to the mode of reception. The three types become further blended through the importance of topoi. The thing that makes topoi so important is not that it allows the three modes to merge, but the recognition in the first part of the 20th century that it provides a common concern. And, although this common concern had been touched upon dating back to the earliest works, the 20th century brought this common concern to the forefront of discussion as a grounds for interpretation. The common concern referred to here is that of what it means to be human? This system of value implemented became more important to not only the reception of the artifice, but inherently important as characteristic of the creation of the artifice. It has only become truly problematic because scholarship has been applied as a principle to writing that predates the 20th century. The result was that it created a concept for defining English Language Literature in its application. The necessity for such a pedagogical paradigm was two-fold: Monetary and Respectability. Two intertwined necessities for scholarship to be pursued. If the purpose of writing is entertainment, then what purpose is there in studying it? The answer should of course be obvious, to clarify, if the purpose was entertainment, it follows that the purpose of studying it would be to develop and improve the product so that it will continue to be consumed. In this way, seemingly no higher purpose seems to be served. Yet, in the process of developing and improving writing, writers are faced with making the artifice being created relevant to the consumer. To that end, the topoi employed will attempt to introduce a dimension that reflects the actual conditions of the consumer. Through this practice of development and improvement, the artifice assumes through its creation a commentary on social issues in terms of humanity. Hence, even if the artifice is created merely for entertainment purposes, it must also be understood that implicit in the act of creating the artifice there exists value that is erudite. To put

in context, Joseph Conrad's *The Heart of Darkness* consumed as a simple adventure story, even if the reader is unaware of the history of the colonialization of the Congo, the adventure story through this progression reveals the tremendous harm caused at the time-period in that region by this group of people. The leap that must occur in the consumption of the artifice this way is the connection to the revelation made as the narrator does in fact offer commentary on the situation in the narrative itself in a way that extends beyond the narrative itself. The attempt to make the assertion that Conrad wrote this story with the intention of offering social commentary is a moot point because the social commentary exists in the novel even without Conrad. So powerful is the social commentary of this narrative that it could actually function on a different river at a different point time in an entirely different medium. The reference here is to the originally released version³ of Francis Ford Coppola's "Apocalypse Now". This version of the movie follows the narrative form of Conrad's novel without actually revealing the magnitude of the importance of that social commentary. Like the novel, it offers imagery through the narrative events that allow the social commentary to immerge of its own accord in the consumption of the artifice. This example is a rather easy leap to make. Yet, what makes these journeys so different from the classical journey is that the main character is not the hero. Unlike the narratives of the previous century in which the main character is set as the hero⁴ of the artifice, from the turn of the 20th century, narrative form utilizes a more voyeuristic tone by adoption of a {main character | narrator} who is always obsessively aware of an objectified hero. The truly remarkable thing about this narrative form is that it is not of the 20th century. Chaucer's *The Canterbury Tales* employs the same narrative form because each of the tales that are related in that poem are related second-hand with a similar voyeuristic tone by {Chaucer | the narrator}. While it may be entertaining to consider that Conrad had Chaucer in mind when he penned his tale, it is rather a pointless pursuit. The social commentary created by both writers is so vastly separated by space

and time that such an assertion comes nowhere close to even being a conceit. Yet today, both Conrad and Chaucer are enshrined in this notion as being the very definition of Literature.

Another, more difficult aspect of this situation is that in order to read Fiction as Literature a great deal of cognitive effort is required. This brings up the issue of why people read fiction. Like all entertainment, fiction is a way of escaping reality. Unlike reading for information, which is the act of finding a grounding in reality for information, fiction acts as a grounding for imagination. If a psychological perspective were assumed, it could be asserted by allowing the imagination to function freely, it relieves the continual tension brought about on by the extreme function of that part of the mind that is employed to understand the world. Yet, like other soft sciences actual proof of this would require the deployment of actual physical observation that is generally employed in mind mapping research. Here again, the notion of soft science and hard science become difficult due to the speculative nature applied to findings. Be that as it may, the cognitive aspect of reading will continually be a taxing exercise regardless of the purpose. It is even possible to assert that through imagination, reading for entertainment works to create a fluid reality which is less reliant on the normal cognitive function of the mind, and uses a part that has more elasticity. Thus, when Fiction is read as Literature the mind must operate in a constant state of flux. The inevitability of *misreading*⁵ in such a state can produce the result of an attempt to read the artifice as Literature without the due attention necessary to be a cognate of the actual meaning. This situation is only made more corrupt through the application of an approach to Literature known as Literary Theory.

Much like the question of humanism that began after World War I, the notion of finding an approach to Fiction began to gain attention. While Drama and the elements of its artifice had begun to receive attention much earlier, the actual state of affairs with English Language Literature—to the exclusion of drama— became linked to challenges imposed through Modernism. This created a tremen-

dous about of confusion as Modernism is in fact an international consideration not limited to a single kind of artifice such as English Language Literature. Although English Language Literature is a form of Art through the nature of its artifice, the considerations of other forms were not hindered through their treatment as third-class baggage as English Language Literature has been until the 20th century. Yet, the function of the study of form in Modernism created a grounding for principles that could be applied to all English Language Literature. To be sure, this type of formalism had already existed in Poetry because of its nearness to Music, but not as a method of understanding; only as a method of understanding fabrication of the artifice.

Formalism, New Criticism, which ever label is used achieved one very important result: the notion of the importance of the text beyond its author and beyond that author's written words became paramount because it made it possible to justify the artifice's inherent importance. Yet, this did create a very important problem. How is that inherent importance measured in terms of all creative writing? It is this question that leads to the distinction between Literature and Fiction and provides for the notion that while some Fiction is worthwhile through its message, other Fiction is mere fodder for the masses, which was the distinction made in 1829 when the subject was taken up as a serious pursuit for scholarship. The devices used to make this distinction were dependent on Formalism. It was through the application of these devices that the artifice's meaning, and therefore its message, could be discerned and extemporized upon in relation to that other element called the Human Condition.

The devices that shaped the concepts of Formalism still serve as the foundation for teaching English Language Literature today. Yet, for all its value in answering that all important question concerning the Human Condition, it has resulted in an axiomatic paradigm through the scholarly application to artifice predating its own conceptualization. This means that with the coalescing nature of this new type of inquiry, a simultaneous reconceptualization that

would systematically create the two divergent forms of Fiction for Entertainment purposes and Fiction for Educational purposes resulted in a new form of necessitated marginalizing practice. To be precise, Literature marginalizes parts of itself in order to achieve its own worth.

The main tool in this necessitated marginalizing practice became Eliot's application of "the Objective Correlative." It is important to be mindful of the fact, that the concern being discussed is related to the consumption of the artifice, and that this discussion does not consider creation of the artifice as being necessary to consider beyond the scope of creation. Referencing Eliot tends to confuse scholars due to the fact that Eliot's concern became dually applied. The understanding that an artist creates, while the scholar consumes in order to discuss meaning has both hindered and muddled the production of scholarship for the last 100 years. That being understood, the necessitated marginalizing practice makes it possible to examine the literary devices in a seemingly scientific manner. Further, Eliot's notion was directed at the re-experiencing of sensory perception through the creation of an artifice that mimics in an Aristotelian sense implying that meaning is secondary to the evoked emotional response. The crux is that emotional responses, while similar, are not universal and therefore cannot be discussed in any real scientific way. There may be similitudes in empathetic response but at some point it universalizing this definition of each response and creates the situation in which the universal replaces the individual⁶. The individual does not reemerge in fiction in English until the 21st century.

Endnotes

¹The term English Language Literature is used as a replacement for English Literature due to the inaccuracy of the latter which implies that all Literature produced in English is in essence part of Great Britain's cannon. This issue was first encounter in the early 90's in the U.S., at which time U.S. faculties were attempting to change the name of the Department from English Language and Literature to English and American Language and Literature.

² See Peter Barry's text *Beginning Theory: Introduction to Literary Theory and Culture*.

³ The "Full Director's Cut" includes a grounding in the actual historical context of the French Colonialization that disrupts the signification through a dialog that limits the responsibility for the situation of the narrative.

⁴ Care must be taken with the concept of "hero" as there have been a great deal of discussion in scholarship that mostly confuses it with the "hero" in Classical Literature. This usage refers to the notion that the narrative form is built upon a wheel in which each of the spokes are connected to this central hub that is the main character.

⁵ Misreading places fault on incorrect parsing of information in the process of acquisition, which although possible at times, this usage differs in that through inattention caused by the divergence of the mind in this state of flux, the perceived meaning becomes misdirected.

⁶ The term "individual" here can be dangerous due to the isolationist ideology at the turn of the 20th century.

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